

REACH Substance Evaluation of TCP

Petra van Kesteren,¹ W.P. Jongeneel,² N.G.M. Palmen,²
M. Beekman¹

¹ Bureau REACH, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Bilthoven, the Netherlands.

² Centre for Safety of Substances and Products, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), Bilthoven, the Netherlands.

Corresponding author:

Petra van Kesteren

petra.van.kesteren@rivm.nl

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REACH, substance evaluation, human health, risk management

ABBREVIATIONS

ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
TCP	Tris (methylphenyl) phosphate

ABSTRACT

REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals) is a European regulation to improve the protection of human health and the environment from the risks that can be posed by chemical substances. The substance evaluation is a specific process under REACH, carried out by Member States, to clarify whether the use of a substance poses a risk to human health or the environment. The Netherlands started a substance evaluation on tris(methylphenyl) phosphate (TCP) in 2014. This evaluation resulted in a formal request for information related to i.e. neurotoxicity and exposure assessment, which shall be provided by the manufacturers of TCP.

INTRODUCTION

Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) is a European regulation adopted to improve the protection of human health and the environment from the risks that can be posed by chemicals.¹ REACH places the burden of proof on

companies. To comply with the regulation, companies must identify and manage the risks linked to the substances they manufacture and market in the EU. They have to demonstrate to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) how the substance can be safely used, and they must communicate the risk management measures to the users. Registration is required to substances that are manufactured or imported in quantities of one ton or more per year per registrant.

The substance evaluation is a specific process under the REACH regulation. Its aim is to clarify whether the manufacture or uses of a registered chemical substance poses a risk to human health or the environment. The substance evaluation process is triggered as a result of risk-based concerns that have not been adequately addressed in the registration process. It involves an assessment of the data in all registration dossiers from all registrants specific to the same substance. The aim is to identify whether new information is needed from the registrants to address and evaluate the concern. Substance evaluation is carried out by the member states; ECHA has a coordinating role in the substance evaluation process.

A substance evaluation follows several steps, including the evaluation of the registration dossier(s), drafting a decision, commenting periods for proposing amendments by the registrants, other member states and ECHA, and reaching unanimous agreement by the Member State Committee (MSC). The Decision contains the grounds for the risk-based concern and the justification for the information request. After agreement, the Decision is sent to the Registrant(s) and new information shall be provided before the given deadline. These newly provided data are evaluated by the evaluating Member State within 12 months of receiving the information and conclusions are drawn relating to potential follow-up actions. Possible follow-up includes a request for new information, regulatory risk management actions or no action when the initial concern has been satisfactorily addressed and no further concern remains.

The Netherlands started a substance evaluation on

tris (methylphenyl) phosphate (TCP) in 2014. The initial concerns were a concern on the persistence, bioaccumulation and toxicity (PBT) and wide dispersive use. Additional concerns that were included during the evaluation were related to substance identity and human health, and attention was paid to exposure assessment and derivation of derived no effect levels (DNELs). A draft decision was made and after taking all the steps following procedure the decision was agreed upon by the MSC in 2016.

The ECHA's Decision includes six requests,² summarized here:

1. *In vitro* dermal absorption study using OECD 428.
2. 90-day repeated dose neurotoxicity study in the rat, by inhalation nose only, according to test OECD 424, using a representative composition of the registered substance. Adaptations and additions to the test are described.
3. Justification for the deviation from the ECHA Guidance in the derivation of the DNELs.
4. An exposure assessment for the exposure scenario of pilots and cabin crew to the registered substance during flights, including a calculation of the inhalation and dermal exposure and calculation of the RCR by combining the RCR (inhalation) and RCR (dermal).
5. Provide all available information on the content and anonymized results of questionnaires, medical and clinical investigations and industrial hygiene assessments among TCP exposed workers, and the study of a possible causal relationship between TCP exposure and neurotoxic complaints.
6. Detailed information on worker exposure for all scenarios, to allow an assessment of the adequacy of the risk management measures in place for the registered substance to be made. Specifications were indicated.

The deadline for providing the requested information is 2

August 2018. When the new information is provided, the Netherlands, as evaluating Member State, will evaluate the data and decide whether the new information submitted meets the requests in the decision. Further, if the evaluating Member State Competent Authority (MSCA) considers that further information is still needed to clarify the concern, a new draft decision may be written.

References

1. ECHA. European Chemical Agency. <https://echa.europa.eu/nl/home>.
2. ECHA. Information on chemicals. <https://echa.europa.eu/nl/information-on-chemicals/evaluation/community-rolling-action-plan/corap-table/-/dislist/details/0b0236e180694747>.